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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable reports on the progress that has been achieved in the direction of the dose-effective imaging of organic molecules. We report several essential experimental advancements, including a successful experimental scheme of ghost imaging that could be realised in Modena without the need of travelling. Overall this deliverable includes material for at least 3 papers and a patent.

The restriction on travels due to Covid-19 imposed hard constraints on the performance of the intended experiment. The complete experiment on proteins would, in fact, have required the simultaneous presence of three groups at the microscope in Jülich: FZJ personnel for main operation on the microscope, people from MU for the cryomicroscopy part, and people from CNR for the lateral control of software and for the coordination of the experiment. Moreover, the preparation of the experiment required the intervention of FEI personnel. Unfortunately, in spite of the partial release of the restrictions during the extra 6 months allotted to Q-SORT, for the reasons given above these conditions were impossible to meet. This was unforeseeable at the moment the project extension was asked.

Given these hard constraints, we chose the combination of experimental activities that allowed us to achieve the greatest possible amount of project goals. In fact, Q-SORT scientists achieved more than what was foreseen; novel results include:

- 1) the first patentable phase plates of different design (designed in WP3 D3.4 for protein recognition) able to control up to 24 electrodes by multiplexing the initial 8 inputs.
- 2) the first computational ghost imaging experiment in microscopy and its optimization for low dose regime
- 3) a state of the art neural network control for an efficient prediction of the generated caustic pattern.

Two approaches to the protein recognition were chosen at the end of WP3: a) the extension of the OAM sorter with an additional programmable phase plate. Such approach is referred to as GOAMS (generalised OAM sorter) in D3.2 as b) the computational ghost imaging with increasingly complex masks. Under the given constraints, it was found that the computational ghost imaging approach (D3.2, task 3.1 & 3.2) was the most appropriate and effective to pursue - enabling the greatest advancement. This development is also consistent with contingency plan #6 "Test random or Hadamard sparse sampling".

The results have been also written as a manuscript that is going to be submitted soon.

The hardware for the 3-element GOAMS (i.e. the second approach that was found to be most promising in WP3) was also developed, with the design of an additional element that allowed the recognition of the radial degree of freedom. Such extended "protein specific" phase modulator (D3.4) was also finished and tested as one of the design of the programmable phase plates.

As for the technical development of the apparatus, we will show here the deep-learning algorithms for protein imaging with automatic acquisition. The phase plate and its related deep-learning

software for driving it are opening a new promising route to innovation for future projects, for a patent, and for real applications of the MEMS technology.

Therefore this document is divided in 3 parts

1. the realisation and testing of the Protein-specific phase plates also named here “programmable phase plates”
2. The manuscript on the development of the Computational ghost imaging and the strategy for its experimental control through neural network and optimisation strategy.
3. An appendix with the manuscript on the experimental realisation of optical development of the Computational ghost imaging with TEM-inspired dynamic phase masks

Chapter 1: Protein specific phase plates and devices

As already discussed in the previous deliverable D3.4, one of the aims of this project was to create programmable phase plates with a large number of contacts using the multiplexing technology, also with the aim to patent this idea. The main motivation for the device was to use it as a tool in the proteins discrimination and in particular in the two schemes of “computational ghost imaging” and in “generalized sorter”.

Given the importance of this device as a tool in Q-SORT and in general in MEMS-based electron optics we show here in large details its characterization.

This section is aimed to demonstrate the working device.

1.1 Fabrication workflow

In order to fabricate such devices, the fabrication process flow reported in Fig. 1 was initially adopted.

The flow represented in Fig. 1 was already commented on deliverable D3.4 and is reported again here for the reader’s convenience. In the first fabrication experiments, the process was executed on n-type bulk wafers up to step 20 in order to test the electronic circuits before fabricating the final devices on SOI (Silicon On Insulator) substrates. The electrical measurements performed on the fabricated samples after metallization revealed severe insulation problems between the p-doped regions in the layout. The reason for such problem was not immediately clear, and consequently some specific experiments were carried out to investigate this phenomenon. In these experiments, the modified process flow illustrated in Fig. 2 was adopted, in which three new masks (MASK0, PWELL and PDOP2) were introduced.

Figure 1: First-trial fabrication process flow for IC/MEMS integration in the programmable sorter.

Figure 2: Modified fabrication process flow for IC/MEMS integration in the programmable sorter (first version).

Mask MASK0 was used to facilitate the alignment of the subsequent masks by etching alignment marks on silicon at the beginning of the process (step 2 in Fig. 2), whereas masks PDOP2 and PWELL were used to split the p-type low concentration doping process on the p-well of the diodes (in which mask PWELL was used) and on the diffused resistors (in which mask PDOP2 was used). In this way, a longer annealing could be adopted for the diode p-wells (step 4), adopting a shorter one for the diffused resistors (step 5), possibly avoiding insulation problems due to excessive lateral diffusion of boron. In the newly designed masks, some test structures for p-well doping insulation that could be measured by directly probing the silicon surface were introduced, in order to check possible isolation problems in the early stages of the processing. From the results of such tests, it was clear that the main source of the isolation problems between p-type doped regions was a phenomenon of auto-doping produced on the n-type substrate by the very wide p+ doped regions in the layout, during the initial steps of the gate oxidation of the MOS capacitors (step 7 in Fig. 2). In order to avoid this phenomenon, the new process flow reported in Fig. 3 was adopted, in which the p+ doped regions were covered by a low-temperature deposited

SiO₂ layer to prevent boron out-diffusion, and consequently the auto-doping effect, before oxidation.

Figure 3: Modified fabrication process flow for IC/MEMS integration in the programmable sorter (second version).

With the new flow, all the isolation problems were solved and the correct parameters on the electronic circuit were obtained, as was verified by wafer-level electrical measurements on the bulk test samples. Afterwards, the complete IC-MEMS devices were produced with the developed process (Fig. 4).

1.2 Circuit characterization

In this section we will test the performance of the integrated filters that should separate the different frequencies. The ideal filter should have a non-zero transfer only for the chosen frequency . Unfortunately this is not possible with any set of linear filters formed by the integrated capacitors and resistors.

On the fabricated devices, the transfer characteristics of the electronic filters were measured (Fig. 5), showing a reasonable agreement with the simulated circuits reported in previous deliverable D3.4.

Figure 4: Measured transfer characteristics of electronic filters integrated in programmable sorter prototypes.

Other tests were carried out using signals generated by the readout electronics already described in D3.4, by measuring the voltage produced by the rectifying stages connected to the outputs of the four different filters utilized on each input channel of the programmable devices. The typical result of such a test is reported in Tab. 1 and Fig 4, showing the rectified voltages generated by input DC or sinusoidal signals at different frequencies with a fixed amplitude of 5 V. As can be observed from the data reported in the table, the results of these tests are also in reasonable agreement with the simulated behaviour of the multiplexing circuit.

Table 1. Tests on filter outputs after signal rectification.
Input signal is 5 V at the frequency corresponding to the column name.
 Output on each channel after filter is shown

	DC	5 kHz	75 kHz	1 MHz
Low-pass filter	3.86 V	0.45 V	0.36 V	0.47 V
5 kHz Pass-band filter	0.42 V	1.72 V	0.61 V	0.63 V
75 kHz Pass-band filter	0.42 V	0.60 V	1.80 V	0.48 V
High-pass filter	0.43 V	0.39 V	0.50 V	1.91 V

Figure 5: Graphical representation of the tab 1

The correlation matrix between applied voltage and electrode output is, as expected, reasonably close to diagonal. Since the system is linear the non-diagonal terms can be removed by a compensation with a detuning of the other channels.

1.3 General design description

As anticipated in D3.4 the devices are meant for the protein discrimination based on ghost imaging or generalized sorter where the additional MEMS would sort the radial degree of freedom.

The images below show optical images of the working devices. As anticipated in D3.4 the devices are designed for the protein discrimination. The first set of designs are based on a series of multipoles. The idea is that by combining two of them we can produce a sufficiently

wide range of probes. For example D3.4 showed that Zernike polynomials were a perfect basis for ghost imaging.

Figure 6: Optical microscope images of the different kind of devices. An image of a couple of complete MEMS is also shown.

Additional designs like the second one in figure 6 are meant to provide sufficiently non “harmonic” phase (i.e. $\nabla^2 \varphi = 0$) for single element in order to avoid the need for an alignment and use two devices in the electronic column. The third device is meant to be used for the phase flattening of the radial degree of freedom working as third phase element on the radial phases after a standard OAM sorter.

The figures presented here show also the part of the integrated control electronics that allows to manipulate more bias with the same pin. We present here the electrical characterization of the circuit showing the independent drive of all channels.

1.4 Tests on TEM

As additional test we tried also directly the full devices inside the microscope. An appropriate generator for 6 channels each with 4 frequencies has been created (the black box here). It is shown here along with the Labview control software.

Figure 7. Images of the experiments with the signal generator and its connection to the TEM in Modena

Figure 8: In here are reported in a) a stereo-optical microscope image of a custom MEMS device mounted in the Nano-Ex I-V sample holder where it is possible to notice part of the integrated circuits used to create a multiplexing system that allows from 6 externally biased contact pads to control 24 electrodes. In b),c) and d) are reported the Out-Of-Focus Low-Mag images of three different early prototype MEMS chips with different electrode geometries.

In Fig. 8 are shown an optical image of a MEMS chip mounted inside the holder (a) and in b),c) and d) Low-Mag Out-of-focus TEM images of MEMS devices with different electrodes geometries.

Figure 9: From a) to e) are shown out-of-focus images of the electrodes of one of the early prototype MEMS devices (figure 1 (b)) with integrated circuits for multiplexing. The out-of-focus images clearly show the effect of an applied electrostatic potential on the electrodes as a bulging. a) shows the image of the device where the electrodes are all grounded; b) shows the image where the n-doped substrate is biased at 10V; c) shows an image similar to b) but with a 10V DC potential applied to one of the contacts (here a red star is placed on top of the electrodes affected by the applied bias); d) shows an image similar to b) but with a 10V sinusoidal potential of frequency 10kHz applied to the same contact as c); e) shows an image similar to b) but with a 10V sinusoidal potential of frequency 100kHz applied to the same contact as c).

In Figure 9 c),d) and e) an example of the effect of the applied electrostatic bias is clearly visible, in particular in c) a constant bias is able to “activate” three different electrodes, while a AC signal of frequency 10 kHz (d) applied to the same contact is able to “activate”/polarize just two electrodes, and lastly, (e) an AC signal of frequency 100 kHz activates only one electrode. For a better visualisation of the effect of the applied potential on the electrodes a red star has been placed on the electrodes, which showed a visible effect.

Form this we could calculate the correlation matrix and correct for the cross talk up to produce a separate control of each electrode.

Chapter 2: Ghost imaging

ABSTRACT: *Transmission electron microscopes (TEM) achieve high-resolution imaging by transmitting electrons through the samples to form an image. While a TEM can achieve a higher resolution than optical microscopes, they face challenges of damage to samples during the high-energy processes involved. It is therefore desirable to limit the required electron dose as much as possible. One possible approach to achieve this goal is through ghost imaging, an established technique in optical imaging where modulated intensity patterns are used to illuminate the sample and the images are reconstructed using a bulk detector measurement and knowledge of the patterns. The proof of principle detailed in this article draws inspiration from a simple, six-pin charged device that can induce an electrostatic field capable of creating phase shifts in electron beams. Complex intensity patterns are then created in the far field by randomly turning the pins on and off. An optical analogy using a spatial light modulator to mimic this six-pin device is presented here. Our results show a viable image reconstruction, laying the foundation for future exploration of the robustness of this phase modulation approach with different objects, under different signal-to-noise conditions and testing compressed sensing approaches for analogous reduction in overall beam illumination in electron microscopy.*

2.1 Introduction

Optics is a thriving field with a huge range of applications, that go well beyond imaging a sample in a microscope. Most of these depend on the ability to produce structured light waves, in an arbitrary way, beyond what ordinary cylindrically symmetric lenses can do. The concept of structured waves has been recently extended also to matter waves, primarily electrons. Structuring electron waves paved the way to the production of vortex electron beams [1], self-accelerating beams [2], non-diffracting beams [3] but also orbital angular momentum analysers [4]. In the case of electron beams, an arbitrary way of flexibly programming a beam does not exist. Herein lies the value of the approach presented where we use optical elements and light shaping technologies to emulate existing pin-based modulation techniques from electron microscopy as a proof-of-principle for generating phase masks and testing image reconstruction with currently available technologies.

Single-pixel imaging systems use time-varying phase or amplitude masks, to spatially sample the scene with a set of intensity patterns, and then measure the total transmitted (or reflected) power with a single detector [5]. The signal from this detector is proportional to the overlap integral between the image and the intensity pattern, and by measuring the signal for a wide variety of patterns it is possible to invert the data and obtain an image of the scene. The potential appeals of this single-pixel approach are two-fold. First, that single-pixel detectors cover a wide range of operating wavelengths, and/or have faster response times than detector arrays. Second, using compressed sensing techniques, an image can be obtained with fewer measurements than would be required for raster scanning, as illustrated in [6]. This ability to image with fewer measurements potentially increases the frame rate and/or reduces the exposure of potentially fragile samples to the illumination.

Using these single-pixel techniques, novel imaging systems have been developed that include imaging at Terahertz wavelengths [7], time-of-flight imaging [8, 9], and imaging sensitive to fluorescent lifetime [10]. As an alternative to the electromagnetic spectrum, electron beams can also be used for imaging, yet at much shorter length scales. The time-independent wave equations for the light and electron are perfectly analogous [11]. This analogy is the basis of the electron optics, where components like lenses are defined with the similar nomenclature as for light. However, light optical elements are inherently easier to build and SLMs that shape the optical beams in a programmable, and near arbitrary way, do not explicitly exist for electrons. Although single-pixel imaging has previously been introduced for specialized electron imaging systems [12], the barrier to more general use is indeed the difficulty in creating the equivalent of an SLM.

In the context of electron beams, holographic plates [11] laid the foundation for applications related to electron beams. However, these are passive elements and cannot be addressed like light SLMs do, and their construction requires difficult, nanoscale machining using focused ion beams (FIB) and lithography. A most welcome recent development has been the introduction of active optical elements or programmable phase plates [13]. These are based on simple electrostatic elements to be positioned along the beam path. Two technological solutions are currently available: the research group led by Verbeeck has been developing devices based on Einzel lenses. These work like individual pixels of an optical spatial light modulator but the number of addressable points are few in comparison [13]. An additional challenge is related to the difficulty to bias and drive many connections from outside the microscope column. Other groups are aiming at using separated electrodes to define specific phase landscapes in a wider area: whereas the solution is defined everywhere, the phases φ are limited by the harmonic condition $\nabla^2\varphi = 0$ everywhere except on the electrodes [14]. After the early experiments with material-based electron holograms, it is becoming obvious that material crossing with the electron beam should be reduced as much as possible in the microscope optics as it deteriorates the beam coherence and/or intensity.

The most trivial element thus far is a simple metallic needle[15]. The definition of the electrostatic field around a charged microtip has been indeed one of the first studies in this field [16, 17], wherein charge applied to these needles induces a phase shift, around the tip, to the electron beam. Interestingly, the phase shift generated by a metallic needle was recognized as key to implement the OAM sorter [18]. Most importantly, metallic needles have been demonstrate to produce complex tuneable caustic phenomena [19]. The optical analogy investigated in this article is inspired by the charged microtips approach, designed by Matteucci et al. [16]. The six needles arranged as shown in Fig 1, form a simple and elegant geometry and allows for the realization of complex illumination patterns, which can be exploited for image reconstruction and testing approaches to improve electron microscopy.

2.2 Methods and Results

Figure 1a reports a SEM image of the device developed for generating the caustic patterns. It can be fitted into the electron microscope thanks to a custom-made aperture holder equipped with housings for 4 x 11 mm MEMS chips with sockets based on those used in the Thermo Fisher NanoEx-i/v specimen holder. MEMS fabrication involved two-dimensional patterning of device electrodes using optical lithography and deep reactive ion etching of silicon-on-insulator wafers featuring a recessed etching isolation technique. It allowed up to 8 electrical pins to be used inside the microscope, by connecting internal to external sockets through the body of each aperture holder.

Figure 1b shows the active region of the device as observed through the TEM. Here we set the numbering convention: the needles will be named according to the numbering reported as labels in the picture. In order to minimize decoherence effect, we further reduce the active region of the device using a 10 μm wide circular aperture (figure 1c). Finally Fig. 1d reports the typical phase produced by the device when biased.

Figure 1: a) SEM image of the electrostatic element. b) Needles numbering convention. c) active region of the device when limited by a 10 μm wide circular aperture. d) simulation of the typical phase pattern produced by the electric field inside the device (nominal biases: $V_1 = -0.71$, $V_2 = -0.89$, $V_3 = -1.96$, $V_4 = 1.13$, $V_5 = -0.89$, $V_6 = 1.750$)

In order to simulate the phase pattern produced by the device we first performed finite elements (FE) calculations of the electrostatic potential produced when a nominal bias of 1 V is applied to one of the needles. The electrostatic potential is then transformed into a phase shift by integrating it along the z direction according to:

$$\Delta\phi = C_E \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} V dz$$

We also exploited the symmetry of the device in order to speed up the calculations: in fact we can distinguish between two central needles (needle 1 and 4) and four lateral one (2, 3, 5, 6).

The prototype phase pattern has been calculated both the main needles (figure 2b) and the lateral needles (figure 2c).

Figure 2: a) model of the device as built within COMSOL. Phase pattern prototype for the central (b) and lateral (c) needles.

The total phase is then evaluated as the linear combination of the 6 prototypes, appropriately rotated, with the 6 nominal biases. The electron wavefunction can then be propagated to the observation plane, where the caustic is formed, by calculating the Kirchhoff-Fresnel integral:

$$\Psi_z(u, v) = \frac{e^{ikz}}{i\lambda z} \iint \Psi_0(x, y) e^{-ik\frac{xu+yv}{z}} dx dy$$

A comparison between a pattern calculated as described above and an experimental pattern obtained applying the same biases to the needles is reported in figure 3. In general the calculations are in good agreement with the experimental patterns. The position of the caustics are well reproduced with minor differences in the background fringes. However, the position of the maxima being more important than the details of the caustic pattern, we can neglect those differences.

Calculating a caustic pattern however is a time consuming process, being the computation time around 1 second on a conventional computer. This time, despite being relatively fast, is not ideal considering that thousands of pattern have to be generated in order to reconstruct the image.

Therefore we followed the approach already reported in [20] and used the simulation algorithm to produce a database of simulated images in random configuration. This database has then been

used to train a convolutional neural network (CNN). For the CNN geometry we opted for a conventional VGG-16. [21]

Figure 3: Comparison between (first column) experimental caustic patterns, (second column) numerically simulated caustic patterns and (third column) patterns simulated using the CNN.

The caustic patterns predicted by the CNN are reported in the third column of figure c), together with their numerically calculated and experimental counterparts.

The CNN only produce a blurred version of the caustic pattern. This is most likely due to the CNN being under dimensioned and to the fact that the contrast of the fringes is actually very faint. Nevertheless, the position and relative intensity of the maxima (if more than one is present) are correctly predicted.

In order to test if the level of accuracy reached by the CNN is sufficient for the intended purposes, we compared the image reconstruction obtained using the patterns numerically calculated against the patterns predicted by the CNN.

We proceeded as follows: the numerically generated $P_i^{NG}(x, y)$ patterns have been used to simulate the experiment, i.e. to calculate the GI signals $S_i = \iint P_i^{NG}(x, y)T(x, y)dxdy$ where $T(x, y)$ represents the target image. In the present case T is a Siemens star with six spokes.

The same signals have been used to reconstruct the target image using both the numerically generated patterns and those predicted by the neural network:

$$\begin{aligned} T^{NG}(x, y) &= \sum_i (S_i - \langle S \rangle)(P_i^{NG}(x, y) - \langle P^{NG}(x, y) \rangle)T^{NN}(x, y) \\ &= \sum_i (S_i - \langle S \rangle)(P_i^{NN}(x, y) - \langle P^{NN}(x, y) \rangle) \end{aligned}$$

As a comparison we report in figure 4, two series of reconstructions made with an increasing number of patterns. On the top row there are the images reconstructed using the numerically simulated patterns T^{NG} while in the bottom row the image T^{NN} reconstructed from the patterns predicted by the neural network.

Figure 4: comparison between the GI reconstruction performed using the numerically calculated images (top row) and the pattern predicted by the CNN (bottom row).

Figure 4 demonstrates that the P^{NN} patterns can be successfully used to produce the reconstruction. In fact, for every level of accuracy (number of pattern used in the reconstruction) the two reconstructed images T^{NG} and T^{NN} have the same resolution. As a matter of fact the T^{NN} patterns, being smoother than originals, produce a less grainy image.

The high speed of the CNN in reproducing the caustic patterns can also be exploited to optimize the image reconstruction.

The algorithm works as follows. A pool of caustic patterns is randomly generated (we found 20 patterns to be a reasonable compromise between computation time and performances) and the best one among the pool is selected. The best pattern is used to perform a measurement and to improve the reconstruction.

The selection algorithm is based on the Kullback–Leibler divergence:

$$D_{KL}(P||Q) = \sum_x P(x) \log \log \left(\frac{P(x)}{Q(x)} \right)$$

Where **P** represents the data, the observations, or a measured probability distribution. Distribution **Q** represents instead a theory, a model, a description or an approximation of **P**. The Kullback–Leibler divergence is then interpreted as the average difference of the number of bits required for encoding samples of **P** using a code optimized for **Q** rather than one optimized for **P**.

In other words, it is the amount of information lost when **Q** is used to approximate **P**.

As a demonstration we present here two series of reconstructions made with an increasing number of patterns. On the top row the patterns are randomly generated. On the bottom row we used the optimization algorithm. Clearly the image reconstruction obtained using the selection algorithm has more resolution.

Figure 5: Reconstruction of a Siemens star target image using an increasing number of caustic patterns (500-1000-2000-5000-10000). In the top row the patterns are randomly generated, in the bottom row the patterns are generated using our selection algorithm.

Also the electron dose is used in a smarter way: more electrons are used where needed, that in present case means in the centre of the target and along the edges of the radial sectors, regions where more resolution is needed.

As a demonstration, figure 3 reports the electron dose for the two reconstructions performed with 5000 patterns.

Figure 6: total electron dose after 5000 patterns are used to produce the image reconstruction on the left side in the case of random generated patterns (top row) and using our selection algorithm (bottom row).

Figure 7: Preliminary data for a protein silhouette and a star using 3500 experimental voltage configurations.

As a further demonstration we show here actual preliminary data for a protein silhouette and a star using 3500 experimental voltage configurations. For the protein this corresponds to less than $3 \text{ e}/\text{\AA}^2$ that is the expected dose.

This is indeed a first ghost imaging and it is the first step toward a dose reduction but we need strong “a priori” information and a more flexible phase plate in order to further optimise the choice and reduce sensibly the dose and increase the resolution.

Conclusions

We provided a proof of concept for electron computational ghost imaging. We also demonstrated that it is possible to train a neural network to reliably predict the shape of an electron caustic generated by an arbitrary distribution of electrodes, albeit without extreme accuracy. The trained neural network was then implemented in a computational ghost imaging algorithm, where it was

used to experimentally generate the patterns used in the reconstruction of the target image. We finally exploited the network to generate a batch of candidate caustics and estimate the best one to use in the reconstruction. This proves that electron computational ghost imaging is feasible and that the technique can reach sub-nanometer resolution while using low electron doses and a reduced number of patterns, making this approach viable to study sensitive samples.

References

- 1) Verbeeck, J., Tian, H. & Schattschneider, P. Production and application of electron vortex beams. *Nature* 467, 301–304, DOI: 10.1038/nature09366 (2010).
- 2) Goutsoulas, M. & Efremidis, N. K. Dynamics of self-accelerating electron beams in a homogeneous magnetic field. *Phys. Rev. A* 103, 013519, DOI: 10.1103/PhysRevA.103.013519 (2021).
- 3) Grillo, V. et al. Generation of nondiffracting electron Bessel beams. *Phys. Rev. X* 4, 011013, DOI: 10.1103/PhysRevX.4.011013 (2014).
- 4) Grillo, V. et al. Measuring the orbital angular momentum spectrum of an electron beam. *Nat. Commun.* 8, 1–6, DOI: 10.1038/ncomms15536 (2017).
- 5) Gibson, G. M., Johnson, S. D. & Padgett, M. J. Single-pixel imaging 12 years on: a review. *Opt. Express* 28, 28190–28208, DOI: 10.1364/oe.403195 (2020).
- 6) Kallepalli, A., Innes, J. & Padgett, M. J. Compressed sensing in the far-field of the spatial light modulator in high noise conditions. *Sci. Reports* 11, 1–8, DOI: 10.1038/s41598-021-97072-2 (2021).
- 7) Stantchev, R. I. et al. Noninvasive, near-field terahertz imaging of hidden objects using a single-pixel detector. *Sci. Adv.* 2, 1–6, DOI: 10.1126/sciadv.1600190 (2016).
- 8) Sun, M.-J. et al. Single-pixel three-dimensional imaging with time-based depth resolution. *Nat. Commun.* 7, 1–6, DOI: 10.1038/ncomms12010 (2016).
- 9) Sun, M.-J. & Zhang, J.-M. Single-pixel imaging and its application in three-dimensional reconstruction: A brief review. *Sensors* 19, DOI: 10.3390/s19030732 (2019).
- 10) Futia, G., Schlup, P., Winters, D. G. & Bartels, R. A. Spatially-chirped modulation imaging of absorption and fluorescent objects on single-element optical detector. *Opt. Express* 19, 1626–1640, DOI: 10.1364/oe.19.001626 (2011).
- 11) Shiloh, R., Lereah, Y., Lilach, Y. & Arie, A. Sculpturing the electron wave function using nanoscale phase masks. *Ultramicroscopy* 144, 26–31, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ultramic.2014.04.007> (2014).
- 12) Shwartz, S. Single-pixel imaging with high-energy electromagnetic radiation and particles. *Sci. Bull.* 66, 857–859, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scib.2021.01.019> (2021).

- 13) Verbeeck, J. et al. Demonstration of a 2x2 programmable phase plate for electrons. *Ultramicroscopy* 190, 58–65, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ultramic.2018.03.017> (2018).
- 14) Ruffato, G., Rotunno, E. & Grillo, V. A general framework for conformal transformations in electron optics. *arxiv* (2020).
- 15) Griffiths, D. J. & Li, Y. Charge density on a conducting needle. *Am. J. Phys.* 64, 706–714, DOI: 10.1119/1.18236 (1996). <https://doi.org/10.1119/1.18236>.
- 16) Matteucci, G., Missiroli, G., Muccini, M. & Pozzi, G. Electron holography in the study of the electrostatic fields: the case of charged microtips. *Ultramicroscopy* 45, 77–83, DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-3991\(92\)90039-M](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-3991(92)90039-M) (1992).
- 17) Beleggia, M. et al. Towards quantitative off-axis electron holographic mapping of the electric field around the tip of a sharp biased metallic needle. *J. Appl. Phys.* 116, 024305, DOI: 10.1063/1.4887448 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4887448>.
- 18) McMorran, B. J., Harvey, T. R. & Lavery, M. P. J. Efficient sorting of free electron orbital angular momentum. *New J. Phys.* 19, 023053, DOI: 10.1088/1367-2630/aa5f6f (2017).
- 19) Tavabi, A. H., Migunov, V., Dwyer, C., Dunin-Borkowski, R. E. & Pozzi, G. Tunable caustic phenomena in electron wavefields. *Ultramicroscopy* 157, 57–64, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ultramic.2015.04.003> (2015).
- 20) Rotunno, E., Tavabi, A. H., Rosi, P., Frabboni, S., Tiemeijer, P., Dunin-Borkowski, R. E., Grillo, V. Alignment of electron optical beam shaping elements using a convolutional neural network. *Ultramicroscopy* 228, 113338, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ultramic.2021.113338> (2021)
- 21) Simonyan, K., Zisserman, A. Very Deep Convolutional Networks for Large-Scale Image Recognition. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1409.1556> (2014)

DELIVERABLE CONCLUSIONS

The scheme of the computational ghost imaging is very innovative in electron microscopy and promises to be a big advantage from protein imaging. The combination of the ghost imaging scheme and of the more sophisticated phase modulator with more contacts will soon permit an even larger flexibility. As a rule of thumb the flexibility of the ghost imaging increases with the number of electrodes so we should be able to make the caustics more and more similar to the proteins and allow for more sophisticated hardware sparse sensing. The combination of this with artificial intelligence and a strong a-priori on the protein will change the way we do imaging of proteins.

Appendix: Computational Ghost imaging - optical study

In this appendix we add the complementary optical studies that lead to a further paper that will be also soon submitted. It describes the optical experiments on ghost imaging using TEM-inspired dynamic phase masks

ABSTRACT: *Transmission electron microscopes (TEM) achieve high resolution imaging by raster scanning a focused beam of electrons over the sample and measuring the transmission to form an image. While a TEM can achieve a much higher resolution than optical microscopes they face challenges of damage to samples during the high energy processes involved. Here, we explore the possibility of applying computational ghost imaging techniques adapted from the optical regime to reduce the required illumination intensity. The technological lack of the equivalent high-resolution, optical spatial light modulator for electrons means that a different approach needs to be pursued. Using the optical equivalent, we show that a simple six-pin charged device to modulate the illuminating beam, alongside a novel reconstruction method to handle the resulting highly non-orthogonal patterns, is capable of producing images comparable in quality to a raster-scanned approach with much lower peak intensity.*

Raster scanning a focused beam of light or electrons and measuring the transmission is a simple approach to creating an image in the absence of complicated detector arrays. An alternative approach that has been pioneered in the optical regime has been measuring the transmission of the sample when illuminated with more complicated spatial patterns. This approach, often referred to a classical computational ghost imaging inverts knowledge of the known patterns and their measured transmission to reveal the image. Furthermore, the inversion can be constrained using known image properties (e.g. sparsity of spatial frequencies) such that the image can be estimated from fewer measurements than would have been required by a raster scan; a form of compressed sensing [1], [2].

The potential advantages of the computational ghost imaging approach are two-fold. First, that single element detectors cover a wide range of operating wavelengths, and/or have faster response times than detector arrays. Second, when combined compressed sensing techniques, an image can be obtained with fewer measurements [3], [4]. This ability to image with fewer measurements potentially increases the frame rate and/or reduces the exposure of potentially delicate samples to the illumination.

Using these computational ghost imaging techniques, novel imaging systems have been developed that include imaging at terahertz wavelengths [5], time of flight imaging [6], [7], and imaging sensitive to fluorescent lifetime [8]. As an alternative to the electromagnetic spectrum, electron beams can also be used for imaging but at much shorter length scales. Since the time-independent wave equation for the light and electrons are perfectly analogous [9] components like lenses for electron beams are defined with the similar nomenclature as for light. However, optical elements for light are inherently easier to build and spatial light modulators (SLMs) that shape the optical beams in a programmable, and near arbitrary way, do not explicitly exist for electrons. Although single-element detector-based imaging has previously been introduced for specialised electron imaging systems [10], the barrier to more general use is indeed the difficulty in creating the equivalent of an SLM.

The choice of mask patterns is key to the performance of the system and key to the type of algorithm used to reconstruct the image. The evolution of ghost imaging has seen an evolution in both experimental setups and algorithms [11], [12]. Although the vast majority of computational ghost imaging and the related work on signal pixel camera uses a spatial modulator position in the image plane of the object, the original work by Shapiro [13] recognised that this need not be the case, rather given any specific modulation, the resulting form of the light field in the plane of the object could be calculated using numerical beam propagation techniques enabling both lens free and far field implementations [14].

Another important aspect of ghost imaging are the algorithms used to recover an image from the measurements and knowledge of the patterns used. This problem can be cast into a simple matrix form:

$$A\vec{x} = \vec{b}$$

where A is a matrix containing the patterns \vec{p}_i^T as rows, \vec{x} represents the (discretised) scene, and \vec{b} is the set of measurements b_i . The methods used to retrieve \vec{x} and thereby an image fall roughly into two categories, offline or online. Offline approaches infer the image from the final complete set of patterns and corresponding measurements. The majority of well-known methods for solving linear systems fall in this category, e.g. the matrix (pseudo)inverse, Newton's method, etc. Conversely, online approaches update a best guess of the image with every new measurement and light pattern. The most common online algorithm involves a straightforward weighted sum of the patterns, where the weights are adjusted based on a statistical interpretation of the measurements:

$$\vec{g}_i = \vec{g}_{i-1} + (b_i - \langle b \rangle_i) \vec{p}_i.$$

Here \vec{g}_i is the best estimate after i patterns and $\langle b \rangle_i$ indicates the mean detector value up to the current pattern, and $\vec{g}_0 = \vec{0}$. This algorithm, which we will refer to as traditional ghost imaging (TGI), has been extensively explored with different setups [15].

Figure A1 – The experimental setup consists of a spatial light modulator that superposes the phase masks onto the beam and illuminates the target in the far-field. The transmitted light is measured by a single element detector (i.e. photomultiplier tube). Light at 633 nm is spatially filtered and expanded to fill the aperture of a spatial light modulator (SLM). The output beam of the laser is filtered using an aperture (P), a 50 mm focal length lens (L_1), precision pinhole ($P_{50\mu}$) and 400 mm focal length lens (L_2). The SLM includes both the six-pin phase masks and a diffraction grating. The latter projects most of the modulated light into the first order, which is selected using a 250 mm focal length lens (L_3) and aperture (P). This light is propagated into the far-field through a combination of lenses (250 mm focal length lens (L_4) and 400 mm focal length lens (L_5)). The beam is propagated into two separate arms using beamsplitter (BS). One arm uses a power meter to measure the laser power and the second arm consists of the target (T). The photomultiplier tube (Thorlabs, PMM02) measures the transmitted light after interaction with the target.

The primary advantage of online reconstruction algorithms lies in the low computational overhead and robustness to undersampling. In the absence of additional constraints, to achieve a reasonable spatial resolution, the number of illumination patterns required is typically equal to the number of pixels in the image. This quickly makes the matrix A from very large, leading to high memory requirements and long computation times for offline methods. Online methods only need to store the current best guess of \vec{x} and the current pattern, and only ever operate on vectors of that size. Moreover, TGI is by its very nature impervious to problems with undersampling and can show approximations to the correct image with comparatively only a handful of measurements.

Both classes of reconstruction method work significantly better when used with orthogonal pattern sets, for example Hadamard matrices [16]–[18], where each mask probes a subset of spatial frequencies. For offline methods this is equivalent to ensuring full row rank, which increases the stability of the matrix inversion results. For TGI, it ensures that each pattern's spatial frequencies are counted democratically in the mean correction term. Either way, in the absence of noise, the result approaches the true image when the number of orthogonal patterns equals the number of pixels.

Figure A2 – Of the many patterns used for reconstruction of the object, these illustrations show the holograms projected on the spatial light modulator (grayscale ranging from 0 – 2π), with the corresponding intensity distribution in the far-field. The far-field projection interacts with the object to result in a corresponding signal measurement by the detector.

If the mask patterns are implemented using a pixelated spatial light modulator, specifying their design to be orthogonal is straightforward (e.g. Hadamard, or similar). If, however, the patterns are produced in other ways, e.g. using natural scattering or with the highly limited modulators available in a TEM, then orthogonality between the patterns can no longer be enforced and the reconstruction algorithms no longer converge to an accurate image. The TGI algorithm will overemphasize the overlapping parts of the patterns. To resolve this issue, we report an alternative approach that is computationally efficient and makes optimal use of patterns regardless of their orthogonality. This alternative method, which we will call orthogonalised ghost imaging (OGI), takes inspiration from the Kaczmarz algorithm for solving linear systems.

OGI essentially takes the projection of each new pattern onto the current best pattern estimate as an extra correction to the mean detector value used in TGI:

$$\vec{g}_i = \vec{g}_{i-1} + [(b_i - \langle b \rangle_i) - (c_i - \langle c \rangle_i)]\vec{p}_i,$$

where $c_i = \vec{p}_i \cdot \vec{g}_{i-1}$ is the predicted signal under the assumption that the previous best estimate is the correct reconstruction. This has the effect of mitigating double counting stemming from non-orthogonality and emphasising actual new information present in the measurement. Note that care needs to be taken such that both the measured and predicted values are correctly scaled to

each other such that the reconstructed image approaches the true image. This is equivalent to ensuring that the quantity $[(b_i - \langle b \rangle_i) - (c_i - \langle c \rangle_i)]$ tends to zero. The approach we adopt here to ensure this scaling is to iteratively normalise the signals such that $\langle c \rangle = \langle b \rangle$ and $\sigma_c = \sigma_b$.

Our experimental apparatus for demonstrating the six-pin approach to computational ghost imaging is shown in Figure 1. The expanded output beam from a HeNe laser is shaped using the six-pin phase mask as displayed on the spatial light modulator (SLM) and propagates into the far-field. These phase masks create an intensity distribution in the far-field that illuminates the object. Figure 2 illustrates example holograms generated from the six-pin modulation and their corresponding calculated patterns in the far-field.

The aberration-corrected SLM operates in a diffractive mode, and therefore, the masks are combined with a phase-grating to diffract the desired pattern to the first-order which is selected by a pinhole in the Fourier-plane. The chosen order is then propagated through the lens system and into two optical paths: (a) laser power meter to monitor the laser power for any variations and (b) ghost imaging system (photomultiplier tube, PMT). The PMT is positioned to collect the transmitted light after interaction with the object. Based on the known voltage applied to each of the pins and the phase change this creates, the calculation of the far-field intensity distribution and the measured signal are used to reconstruct the image, using the algorithms described above.

Figure A3 – Our approach illustrates the viability of using TEM-inspired phase masks for image reconstruction using a new approach to ghost imaging known as orthogonalised ghost imaging (OGI). This approach is ideal for cases such as six-pin phase mask sets, where the pattern set is not orthogonal. The comparison shows (a) randomised raster scan using traditional ghost imaging (TGI), (b) six-pin phase masks using TGI and (c) six-pin phase masks using the proposed OGI technique. In each case, the construction was done using a set of 51200 patterns.

We have shown a successful proof-of-principle of the applicability of transmission electron microscopy-inspired phase masks using a novel approach to reconstruction from non-orthogonal pattern sets. Our results (Figure 3) show the applicability and successful reconstruction using non-orthogonal phase masks, such as those inspired from the six-pin arrangement. The resulting resolution is comparable to a standard raster scan. With an eventual objective of reducing the total illumination/irradiation, these phase masks and their application in far-field imaging is key in producing an analogy to electron microscopy. The phase modulation performed here using a

spatial light modulator can be replicated in TEM with trivial, six-pin needles that introduce the random changes in phase as assessed in this article. Future work will apply techniques of compressed sensing and a series of targets to quantify the resolution achieved by this approach, in addition to testing the robustness of these phase masks in different signal-to-noise conditions in both optical and electron microscopy regimes.

References

- [1] P. Sen *et al.*, “Dual photography,” in *ACM Transactions on Graphics*, Jul. 2005, vol. 24, no. 3, pp. 745–755. doi: 10.1145/1073204.1073257.
- [2] M. F. Duarte *et al.*, “Single-pixel imaging via compressive sampling,” *IEEE Signal Processing Magazine*, vol. 25, no. 2, pp. 83–91, 2008, doi: 10.1109/msp.2007.914730.
- [3] E. Candès and J. Romberg, “Sparsity and incoherence in compressive sampling,” *Inverse Problems*, vol. 23, no. 3, pp. 969–985, Jun. 2007, doi: 10.1088/0266-5611/23/3/008.
- [4] V. Studer, J. Bobin, M. Chahid, H. S. Mousavi, E. Candès, and M. Dahan, “Compressive fluorescence microscopy for biological and hyperspectral imaging,” *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, vol. 109, no. 26, pp. 1679–1687, Jun. 2012, doi: 10.1073/pnas.1119511109.
- [5] R. I. Stantchev *et al.*, “Noninvasive, near-field terahertz imaging of hidden objects using a single-pixel detector,” *Science Advances*, vol. 2, no. 6, pp. 1–6, 2016, doi: 10.1126/sciadv.1600190.
- [6] M.-J. Sun *et al.*, “Single-pixel three-dimensional imaging with time-based depth resolution,” *Nature Communications*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 1–6, Jul. 2016, doi: 10.1038/ncomms12010.
- [7] G. A. Howland, D. J. Lum, M. R. Ware, and J. C. Howell, “Photon counting compressive depth mapping,” *Optics Express*, vol. 21, no. 20, pp. 23822–23837, Oct. 2013, doi: 10.1364/oe.21.023822.
- [8] G. Futia, P. Schlup, D. G. Winters, and R. A. Bartels, “Spatially-chirped modulation imaging of absorption and fluorescent objects on single-element optical detector,” *Optics Express*, vol. 19, no. 2, pp. 1626–1640, 2011, doi: 10.1364/oe.19.001626.
- [9] R. Shiloh, Y. Lereah, Y. Lilach, and A. Arie, “Sculpturing the electron wave function using nanoscale phase masks,” *Ultramicroscopy*, vol. 144, pp. 26–31, Sep. 2014, doi: 10.1016/J.ULTRAMIC.2014.04.007.
- [10] S. Shwartz, “Single-pixel imaging with high-energy electromagnetic radiation and particles,” *Science Bulletin*, vol. 66, no. 9, pp. 857–859, May 2021, doi: 10.1016/J.SCIB.2021.01.019.
- [11] F. Ferri, D. Magatti, L. A. Lugiato, and A. Gatti, “Differential ghost imaging,” *Physical Review Letters*, vol. 104, no. 25, pp. 1–4, 2010, doi: 10.1103/PhysRevLett.104.253603.

- [12] G. M. Gibson, S. D. Johnson, and M. J. Padgett, "Single-pixel imaging 12 years on: a review," *Optics Express*, vol. 28, no. 19, pp. 28190–28208, 2020, doi: 10.1364/oe.403195.
- [13] J. H. Shapiro, "Computational ghost imaging," *Physical Review A - Atomic, Molecular, and Optical Physics*, vol. 78, no. 6, pp. 1–4, 2008, doi: 10.1103/PhysRevA.78.061802.
- [14] A. Kallepalli, J. Innes, and M. J. Padgett, "Compressed sensing in the far-field of the spatial light modulator in high noise conditions," *Scientific Reports*, vol. 11, pp. 1–8, Aug. 2021, doi: 10.1038/s41598-021-97072-2.
- [15] A. Gatti, E. Brambilla, M. Bache, and L. A. Lugiato, "Ghost imaging with thermal light: Comparing entanglement and classical correlation," *Physical Review Letters*, vol. 93, no. 9, p. 093602, Aug. 2004, doi: 10.1103/PHYSREVLETT.93.093602/FIGURES/2/MEDIUM.
- [16] W. K. Pratt, J. Kane, and H. C. Andrews, "Hadamard Transform Image Coding," *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 57, no. 1, pp. 58–68, 1969, doi: 10.1109/PROC.1969.6869.
- [17] N. J. A. Sloane and M. Harwit, "Masks for Hadamard transform optics, and weighing designs," *Applied Optics*, vol. 15, no. 1, pp. 107–114, 1976, doi: 10.1364/ao.15.000107.
- [18] Z. Zhang, X. Wang, G. Zheng, and J. Zhong, "Hadamard single-pixel imaging versus Fourier single-pixel imaging," *Optics Express*, vol. 25, no. 16, pp. 19619–19639, Aug. 2017, doi: 10.1364/oe.25.019619.

ANNEX 1: Referee

Referee1

There is a lot of work in this deliverable and I am sure this will go to 2 or more important publications.

In particular this would be the first time of “computational ghost imaging” in electron microscopy and I think we will hear a lot about that in future.

There seems to be more than proteins recognition : I can see an ongoing revolution on the way imaging is made but what is with the original problem of the protein recognition? How far we are from the application to a real protein. Which is the most promising direction?

Thanks for the comments. After studying theoretically and experimentally all the directions indicated by WP3 we believe that the most promising approach is to use ghost imaging with a sufficiently complex phase plate control of the beam. The largely tunable device in chapter 1 is an important ingredient of the realization of a real ghost imaging. The second element is the use of artificial intelligence as shown again in chapter 1. The third that has evolved in these year is a better “a-priori” information about the protein. The recent success of the alfa-fold project of Google that were not available or little developed at the beginning of the project makes us think that we can use artificial intelligence for both the control of the experiment and to constraint the possible solutions. This will be topic of the coming EIC project in continuation of Q-SORT.

Referee 2

Congratulation for the work. I have a question about ghost imaging. How did you choose the geometry for the 6-pins phase modulator? How do you expect the ghost imaging will work with the new 24 contacts phase modulators?

The pin geometry is a compromise between the need for a reduced occupation of the electron beam with electrodes and the need for exiting from the harmonic phase ($\nabla^2\phi = 0$) plate constraint. It also reminds of a scaled down version of the S1 element of the OAM sorter, it is therefore more easy to interpret its generated caustics. The 24 electrodes design is based also will also implement the use of electrodes inside the beam area that locally break the harmonic constraint corrected with a set of external poles. According to the calculations (see WP3 and deliverable D3.2) for phase object ghost images we need a sufficiently complex set of phase hologram i.e. with violation of the harmonic constraint. The 24 pins is already a promising device.

The pattern you realize with ghost imaging are typically just a couple of probes. It seems that the advantage in terms of dose is given by the fact that you can probe the cross correlation of two points at a time.

With this choice of parameters and magnification the caustics are very concentrated in a few points. In this case the ghost imaging can be interpreted as a probe of correlation but in general the caustic could be very extended and the interpretation is less easy but we could have a net

dose advantage if the caustics are made similar to the object we need to observe which is typically extended.

ANNEX 2: ABBREVIATIONS

SHORT NAME OF PARTICIPANTS

Partner	Country	Short Name
National Research Council (Project scientific coordinator)	Italy	CNR
Forschungszentrum Jülich, Ernst Ruska-Centre for Microscopy and Spectroscopy with Electrons	Germany	FZJ
FEI - Thermo Fisher Scientific	The Netherlands	FEI
The Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light	Germany	MPI
University of Glasgow, Department of Physics and Astronomy	United Kingdom	UG
QED Film & Stage Productions Ltd. - UK	United Kingdom	QED
University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Department of Physics, Informatics, and Mathematics - IT	Italy	UMR
Maastricht University, Maastricht MultiModal Molecular Imaging Inst	The Netherlands	MU

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Consortium Agreement	CA
Description of Action	DoA
Description of Work	DoW
European Commission	EC
Grant Agreement	GA
Kick-off Meeting	KoM

Q-SORT

Deliverable D5.5

Manuscript for paper on lowest dose recognition of protein

Project Management Board	PMB
Work Package	WP
Work Package Leader	WPL